

Knowledge and Perception on Menopause

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Menopause it's one type of natural physiological process in the women's life. The quality of life on menopausal status in the women it's varies significant Studies revealed that women may reduce and avoid the emotional and physiological symptoms of menopause by encourage and educating themselves when approaching this stage of women life cycle.

Design: In this study cross sectional survey was conducted.

Setting: The sample setting is in kansa village.

Sample size: The sample sizes were 40.

Tool: In the study 20 questionnaires items was conducted in randomly sample technique.

Result: The study identified that the 15(37.5%) women have good, 19(47.5%) women have average and the 6(15%) women have poor knowledge and perception score. This study result shows that the pre test means value is 11.7 and standard deviation is 5.13.

KEY WORDS: Knowledge, Menopause, Perception, young-middle age.

BACKGROUND OF STUDY

One type of physiological phase in the women's life cycle is the menopause. The primary cause of this absence of menstruation is a lack of oestrogen hormone release from ovarian follicles. A woman is classified as postmenopausal if she goes more than a year without having her period. Women experience the climacteric symptoms, becoming ill, weak, and unhealthy due to an oestrogen deficiency. The symptoms of climax range from vasomotor dysfunction to physical, psychological, and sexual dysfunction.

Estimates for the average age of menopause around the world range from 45 to 55 years. The average age at menopause in industrialised nations is usually regarded to be 51 years, however figures for developing nations are inconsistent due to methodological issues (WHO, 1996)

Menopause has had a major impact on a woman's life cycle. For this reason, women have health needs that need to change significantly, and it is important that they are aware of the new health risks they face and that there are ways to prevent and mitigate these risks. As we approach this stage of a woman's life cycle, we can reduce and avoid the emotional and physiological symptoms of menopause.

Knowing more about the concept of menopause will help women better and better cope with the changes that accompany menopause? Lack of knowledge about menopause has pointed out that women become more anxious when it comes time to confront menopause, which adversely affects their emotional state. Changing the perception of menopausal women by improving their knowledge of menopausal women can help reduce emotional confusion.

This study showed that the stigma of menopause begins early in life. This is because there is little accurate education or information about this menopause in young middle-aged women unless families and societies emphasize an open and protective perspective. It has also been found that social impact and culture influence how individuals think about menopause. Until recently, it was not common for Indian women to seek counselling for symptoms associated with the transition to menopause.

METHODOLOGY

This study aims to assess the knowledge and perceptions associated with menopause in young to middle-aged (15-49 years) women. A cross-sectional survey was conducted in this survey. The sampling method is randomly selected and 20 questionnaires are used.

The sample setting is the village of kansa. The sample size was 40. The women in this study recognized the importance of menopause and its symptoms. Face-to-face data collection was carried out. It consists of 20 multiple-choice questions. The total score is 20. Evaluated using descriptive and interstitial statistics such as mean, standard deviation, chi-square data. A p-value of 0.05 for & it; was considered statistically significant. Presented in the form of tables and charts.

RESULT

The results have been presented in to the following headings:

Table 1: Sample category, frequency and percentage are distribution based on demographic variables.

N=40

S. no	Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age	12 to 17	07	20%
		17 to 21	11	27.5%
		22 to 30	10	25%
		31 to 45	12	30%
2.	Education	Illiterate	13	32.5%
		10 th pass	15	37.5%
		12 th pass	08	20%
		Graduation	04	10%
3.	State	Gujarat	29	72.5%
		Rajasthan	06	15%
		Maharashtra	02	5%
		Any other	03	7.5%
4.	Occupation of the mother and father	Teacher	09	22.5%
		Talati	08	20%
		Medical worker	04	10%
		Any other	19	47.5%
5.	Religion	Hindu	32	80%
		Muslim	06	15%
		Kristian	01	2.5%
		Any other	01	2.5%
6.	Married life	Unmarried	18	45%
		Married	19	47.5%
		Widow	02	5%
		Divorce	01	2.5%

Table 1:The data in highest percentage (30%)were in the group of 31 to 45,(27.5%) were in the age group of 17 to 21,(25%) were in the group of 22 to 30 and(20%) were in the group of 12 to 17. The data regard to education that highest percentage (37.5%) were in 10th pass,(32.5%) were in Illiterate,(20%) were in 12th pass and (10%) were in Graduation. In the state highest percentage (72.5%) were in Gujarat,(15%) were in Rajasthan,(5%) were in Maharashtra and (7.5%) were in Any other state. The data regard occupation of the mother and father highest percentage (47.5%) were in any other occupation,(22.5%) were in Teacher,(20%) were in Talati and (10%) were in Medical worker. In religion highest percentage (80%) were in Hindu,(15%) were in Muslim and (2.5%) in Kristian and Any other. The data distribution according to that Married life shows that highest percentage (47.5%) were Married,(45%) were Unmarried,(5%) were Widow and (2.5%) were Divorced women.

Fig - frequency and percentage distribution of the level of knowledge

Figure shows frequency and percentage distribution of level of knowledge and perception on menopause in that 15(37.5%) women have good score, 19 (47.5%) women have average score and the 06(15%) women have poor score. In this study good level is considered who women have 15-20 score, Average level is considered who women having 8-14 score and the poor level considered who women having 0-7 score

Table 2: Association of level of Knowledge and perception on menopause among women With Selected Demographic Variables.

S.N	Variable	Category	Frequency	Level of knowledge and perception			Table value	Df Value	Chi-square
				Good	Average	Poor			
1	Age	12 to 17	07	5	1	1	3.14	6	15.043
		17 to 21	11	4	7	0			
		22 to 30	10	4	6	0			
		31 to 45	12	2	5	5			
2.	Education	Illiterate	13	4	5	4	0.43	6	6.55
		10 th pass	15	8	6	1			
		12 th pass	08	2	5	1			
		Graduation	04	1	3	0			
3.	State	Gujarat	29	15	9	5	2.10	6	12.72
		Rajasthan	06	0	5	1			
		Maharashtra	02	0	2	0			
		Any other	03	0	3	0			
4.	Occupation of the mother and father?	Teacher	09	05	3	1	3.14	6	16.114
		Talati	08	0	5	3			
		Medical worker	04	0	2	2			
		Any other	19	10	9	0			

5.	Religion	Hindu	32	14	12	6	0.43	6	6.73
		Muslim	06	1	5	0			
		Kristian	01	0	1	0			
		Any other	01	0	1	0			
6.	Married life	Unmarried	18	10	2	6	4.52	6	20.158
		Married	19	5	14	0			
		Widow	02	0	2	0			
		Divorce	01	00	01	0			

The above table explain the association between the knowledge and perception on menopause among women with their selected demographic variables. The selected socio demographic variables such as age, state, occupation of mother and father and married life of woman were significantly associated with the level of knowledge and perception on menopause. Other selected socio demographic variables such as education and religion were not significantly associated with the level of knowledge and perception on menopause.

DISCUSSION

Menopause is the one type of unique stage in the women reproductive life cycle. The quality of life during menopause varies greatly from woman to woman. In postmenopausal women, life is affected by menopausal symptoms. When menopause occurs, female has an accurate idea of lifespan. In this study, women were more aware and knowledgeable about the physical signs and symptoms of menopause, such as depression, vaginal dryness, irritability, and weakness. Lethargy and physiological symptoms such as incontinence, excessive sweating, and hot flashes. Women know about menopause as a way to overcome pain and symptoms. Surprisingly, though, she is ignorant of hormone replacement therapy. Nearly half of women either have no understanding of HRT or have a preference for traditional therapies over HRT. The findings of this study indicate that the pre-test mean value was 11.7 and the SD was 5.13. The calculated ci square value were less than the table value & checked at the level of 0.05 level. There was significant association between knowledge and perception score of women and selected demographic variables.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this study's findings shed light on how well-informed and how women in Kansa Village perceive the menopause. To eliminate stigmas associated with menopause from the school setting, young women in this village should get education. The findings of this study offer important direction for future training in behavioural modification and exercise aimed at enhancing women's perceptions of this shift in their lives, ultimately enabling them to approach this stage of life in a much more positive manner. This study highlights the need for additional investigation into how women perceive and understand the menopause. The study's findings show that 15 (37.5%) of the women had strong knowledge and perception scores, 19 (47.5%) had average knowledge and perception scores, and 6 (15%) had poor knowledge and perception scores.

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